

Internal Efficiency Performance of Public Secondary Schools in the Division of Quezon: Basis for Intervention Program

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Abstract. This study examined the internal efficiency performance of public secondary schools in the Division of Quezon as a basis for an intervention program. It focused on key indicators, including enrolment, promotion, graduation, survival, failure, repetition, and dropout rates among central and non-central schools over a five-year period. A quantitative descriptive research design was utilized, employing statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, and measures of central tendency. The respondents consisted of school heads and designated personnel from 6 central and 41 non-central public secondary schools selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist and document analysis of school records, including Form 2 and the Learner Information System (LIS). The findings revealed that both central and non-central schools demonstrated generally high internal efficiency, particularly in promotion, survival, and graduation rates. However, none achieved the ideal 100 percent performance across all indicators. Central schools showed slightly higher and more stable performance, while non-central schools exhibited greater variability, especially in failure, repetition, and dropout rates. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference between the two groups in most indicators, except for graduation rate, where central schools performed significantly better. Problems affecting internal efficiency were seldom encountered but were more evident in non-central schools, particularly those related to poverty, health issues, and learner mobility. Schools addressed these challenges through strategies such as academic interventions, parental involvement, and community collaboration. The study concludes that while both school types perform satisfactorily, non-central schools require additional support. A structured intervention program focusing on learner support and stakeholder engagement is recommended to improve overall school efficiency.

Introduction

Education is a cornerstone of national development, and schools serve as the primary institutions tasked with nurturing human capital and driving societal progress. While access to education has expanded significantly in many regions, including the Philippines' Calabarzon area, ensuring that schools operate with optimal effectiveness remains a critical challenge for educators, administrators, and policymakers alike.

Internal efficiency of a school refers on how effectively the institution uses its human, physical, financial, and educational resources to deliver quality learning and achieve its core objectives, while minimizing waste and maximizing the value of inputs. It focuses on optimizing processes within the school system to ensure that resources translate into positive educational outcomes of the learners. The indicators for internal efficiency for schools are measurable metrics used to assess how well the institution utilizes its resources in order to achieve educational outcomes and operational goals. They provide concrete data to identify strengths, gaps, and areas for improvement.

In an era of limited budgets, growing student populations, and evolving educational needs, inefficient use of resources not only constrains a school's capacity to support learning but also perpetuates gaps in quality and access. This study examines

the concept of internal efficiency in schools, focusing on its key dimensions, measurement indicators, and practical implications for institutional improvement. By analyzing current practices and identifying areas for enhancement.

On a global scale, the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) mandates that nations ensure inclusive and equitable quality education. However, the international community continues to grapple with the "last mile" of educational delivery. Globally, internal efficiency—defined by a system's ability to retain students and move them through the cycle without wasting resources on repetition or dropout—is often stymied by geographic disparities (UNESCO, 2023).

Research from the World Bank (2022) consistently highlights that rural or "non-central" schools face a higher risk of inefficiency compared to their urban counterparts. While developed nations have leveraged technology to bridge this gap, many developing regions still struggle with a "Geography of Disadvantage," where a student's proximity to a central hub dictates their likelihood of completion (OECD, 2021).

The Philippine educational system faces a unique challenge: while promotion rates are often high, the graduation and survival rates vary significantly due to socio-economic factors. David and Albert (2022) suggest that students in non-central schools are more vulnerable to external shocks—such as seasonal labor, poverty, and limited instructional materials—creating an "equity gap" that prevents the country from achieving full internal efficiency.

Within the Province of Quezon, this national trend manifests as a localized crisis of completion. Quezon is characterized by a diverse topography, ranging from bustling urban centers to isolated coastal and upland barangays. Performance data from the Division of Quezon (2024) reveals a narrative of resilience, yet it simultaneously exposes a statistical anomaly: the Graduation Paradox.

Through these given scenarios, the researcher would like to investigate the internal efficiency performance of public secondary schools in the Division of Quezon.

Methodology

Research Design

A research design is the arrangement of conditions for the collection and analysis of relevant data that best addresses the research purpose with the minimum expenditure of effort, money, and time (Galero-Tejero, 2011).

In order to provide a precise and trustworthy description of the elements or variables associated with the research questions, this study uses a quantitative research design and a descriptive research methodology. The study employed descriptive statistics, including dispersion or variation measures, central location measurements, central tendency measures, and frequency distributions (Broto, 2006). This method summarizes individual opinions within the group and gives a clear picture of the demographic profiles of the respondents.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the Fourth Congressional District of the Province of Quezon, under the Division of Quezon, Department of Education. The locale was selected because it comprises both central and non-central public secondary schools, which are relevant to the assessment of internal efficiency performance.

The municipalities included in the study were purposively selected to represent the Division of Quezon. These municipalities and their identified schools are as follows: Alabat—Alabat Island National High School; Atimonan—RT Camacho Integrated School, Malinao Ilaya National High School, and Maligaya National High School; Calauag—Rufina P. Trinidad Memorial National High School and Calauag National High School; Gumaca—Villa Perez National High School and Lamong Bay School of Fisheries; Lopez—Lopez Comprehensive National High School and Hondagua National High School; Guinayangan—Aloneros National High School and Dung-awan National High School; Quezon:Severo Tejada Integrated School, Joel B. Arquiza National High School, and Evaristo Macalintal Memorial National High School; and Tagkawayan:Tagkawayan National High School and Bagong Silang National High School.

The selected schools are different in location, size, and type, which gives a good picture of public secondary schools in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. They were chosen because they are close and easy to reach, making it easier to gather data and study how efficient the schools are

Municipality	Schools	Location
Alabat	Alabat Island National High School	Central
Atimonan	Atimonan National High School	Central
	RT Camacho Integrated School	Non-Central
	Malinao Ilaya National High School	Non-Central
	Maligaya National High School	Non-Central
Calauag	Rufina P. Trinidad Memorial National High School	Non-Central
	Calauag National High School	Central School
	San Roque Ilaya National High School	Non-Central
	Lamon Bay School of Fisheries Annex- Capaluhan	Non-Central
	Ananias A. Diamante Integrated National High School	Non-Central
	Villa San Isidro National High School	Non-Central
	Apad National High School	Non-Central
	Sto. Angel National High School	Non-Central
	Sto. Domingo National High School	Non-Central
	Lagay National High School	Non-Central
	Bantulinao Integrated School	Non-Central
Gumaca	Villa Perez National High School	Non-Central
	Lamon Bay School of Fisheries	Non-Central
	Camohaguin National High School	Non-Central
	Bantad National High School	Non-Central
	Gumaca Integrated School	Non-Central
	Villa Perez National High School	Non-Central
	Gumaca National High School	Central
Lopez	Lopez Comprehensive National High School	Central
	Hondagua National High School	Non-Central
	Sta.Catalina National High School	Non-Central
	Pamampangin National High School	Non-Central
	Sto. Nino Ilaya National High School	Non-Central
	Magallanes National High School	Non-Central
	Pisipis National High School	Non-Central
	Lalaguna National High School	Non-Central
	Guites National High School	Non-Central
	Hondagua National High School	Non-Central
	Dao National High School	Non-Central
Guinayangan	Aloneros National High School	Non-Central
	Dung-awan National High School	Non-Central
	Nabangka National High School	Non-Central
Plaridel	Concepcion National High School	Central
Quezon	Severo Tejada Integrated School	Non-Central
	Joel B. Arquiza National High School	Non-Central
	Evaristo Macalintal Memorial National High School	Non-Central
	Pablo D. Maningas National High School	
Tagkawayan	Tagkawayan National High School	Central School
	Bagong Silang National High School	Non-Central
	Cabibihan National High School	Non-Central
	Sanmandelcar National High School	Non-Central
	Kinatakutan National High School	Non-Central
	Mapulot National High School	Non-Central
	Katimo National High School	Non-Central
	Bamban National High School	Non-Central

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Population and Sample

The study includes all central and non-central elementary public secondary schools in the Division of Quezon that are recognized by the Department of Education and have the primary data sources for the study were school principals, teachers, and school records containing information on enrollment, promotion, graduation, survival, failure, repetition, and dropout rates.

This study used purposive sampling because the selected central and non-central schools were accessible to the researcher. This method also addressed practical limitations such as time, distance, and administrative factors, while ensuring the schools chosen were relevant to the study's objectives.

From the total population, 6 central schools and 41 non-central schools were selected as respondents of the study. The school heads and designated school personnel responsible for school records were chosen as respondents, as they are directly involved in monitoring internal efficiency indicators.

This sampling method ensured that the study's findings are representative and reflect the actual internal efficiency performance of schools in the Division of Quezon.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument used in this study is a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist, supported by document analysis of official school records covering the past five years. The instrument was designed to gather data aligned with the research questions of the study and is divided into three major parts.

Part I focuses on the school profile and internal efficiency performance. This part includes (a) the demographic profile of the respondents and (b) the internal efficiency indicators of the schools, namely enrolment rate, promotion rate, graduation rate, survival rate, failure rate, repetition rate, and dropout rate. Data for these indicators were obtained from school records, including Form 2, the Learner Information System (LIS), and other official documents.

Part II determines the common problems encountered by the central and non-central public secondary schools relative to internal efficiency performance.

Part III examines the coping strategies schools employ to address problems related to internal efficiency. This part includes strategies implemented by schools regarding enrolment rate, promotion rate, graduation rate, survival rate, failure rate, repetition rate, and dropout rate.

Data Gathering Procedure

Based on the sub-problems mentioned in the previous chapter, the researcher will create the research questionnaire. The questionnaire will be presented to an expert panel for review and alignment of content. These experts' suggestions and comments will be considered and incorporated into the research questionnaire after all have been addressed. It will be presented to the experts who reviewed the research questionnaire once more. After seeking the experts' approval, the self-developed research questionnaire will also be tested for validity and reliability. It will be administered to seventeen (17) non-respondents and then tested using Cronbach's Alpha. The results will be reported to the statistician for further action, if any. Moreover, the researcher will write a letter of request to the Department of Education (DepEd) Division of Quezon, led by OIC the Schools Division Superintendent, Elias A. Alicaya Jr. The Google link will be used for easy data consolidation. The gathered data from the schools will be tallied, processed, analyzed, and interpreted to address the problems this research aims to address.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical techniques aligned with each research variable to ensure accuracy, comparability, and meaningful interpretation of results. All statistical computations were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), which facilitated efficient data processing, analysis, and validation of results.

For the internal efficiency performance of schools (Research Question 1), the indicators—namely enrolment rate, promotion rate, graduation rate, survival rate, failure rate, repetition rate, and dropout rate—were treated using percentage analysis. These indicators were derived from school records over a five-year period and summarized using mean percentages to describe the overall performance of central and non-central public secondary schools. The use of percentages enabled standardized comparison across school types and over time. Higher values in enrolment, promotion, graduation, and survival rates were interpreted as indicators of stronger internal efficiency, whereas higher failure, repetition, and dropout rates signified areas of inefficiency. Trend analysis was likewise conducted to examine patterns of improvement, decline, or stability across the five-year period.

For the significant difference in internal efficiency performance between central and non-central schools (Research Question 2), the study employed the t-test for independent samples. This inferential statistical method was used to

determine whether statistically significant differences exist between the mean performance of the two groups of schools across all internal efficiency indicators. The use of SPSS ensured accurate computation of test statistics and significance levels, thereby strengthening the reliability of the comparative analysis.

For the problems encountered by schools relative to internal efficiency (Research Question 3), the mean and standard deviation were utilized. The mean determined the level or extent to which specific problems were experienced by the respondents, while the standard deviation measured the variability or consistency of their responses. This combination provided a comprehensive understanding of both the prevalence and dispersion of the identified challenges across schools. Similarly, for the coping strategies employed by schools (Research Question 4), the mean and standard deviation were also applied. The mean described the extent to which specific strategies were practiced, whereas the standard deviation indicated the degree of agreement among respondents regarding their implementation. The use of SPSS in these analyses ensured precise computation and facilitated the identification of commonly adopted strategies as well as variations in practice across different school contexts.

Results and Discussion

The study used a quantitative descriptive research design to analyze the internal efficiency performance of selected public secondary schools using statistical measures such as frequency, percentage, and measures of central tendency. The study was conducted in selected public secondary central and non-central schools in the Fourth Congressional District of the Division of Quezon. The respondents of the study consisted of school heads and designated personnel from 6 central schools and 41 non-central schools selected through purposive sampling in the Division of Quezon. The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist and document analysis of school records, including Form 2 and the Learner Information System (LIS), to gather data on internal efficiency indicators. The researcher developed and validated a questionnaire through expert review and reliability testing, secured permission from the Department of Education Division of Quezon, and collected data from respondents using a Google Form for efficient data consolidation.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analyzed data, this study obtained the following findings:

1. On the Performance of Internal Efficiency of the School

Over the five-year period, both central and non-central schools in the Division of Quezon demonstrated generally high levels of internal efficiency. However, none achieved the target of 100 percent performance across key metrics – enrolment, promotion, graduation, and survival rates. Similarly, they were unable to

- 1.1 Enrolment rate: Central schools (97.47) have a better ability to draw in and keep students, as seen by their continuously slightly higher participation rates than non-central schools (96.35).
- 1.2 Promotion (central-94.88 and non-central-94.54) and survival rates (central-94.88 and non-central-94.54): While both school categories had good average results, central schools' grade-to-grade retention and cohort progression were slightly better.
- 1.3 Graduation rate: Consistently high across all years for both groups, exceeding 97% on average, underscoring effectiveness in ensuring cycle completion.
- 1.4 Failure (central-1.75 and non-central- 2.78) and repetition rates (central-1.97 and non-central- 1.62): Low overall, but non-central schools exhibited greater fluctuations, including a marked increase in one academic year.
- 1.5 Dropout rate (central-1.21and non-central- 1.02): Low overall, though both school categories experienced noticeable spikes in the most recent year, due to external disruptions.

Overall, Central schools displayed more stable performance trends, while non-central schools showed vulnerability to contextual challenges such as resource limitations and geographic dispersion.

2. Significant Difference of Central and Non-Central Schools on the Internal Efficiency

Over the period of the five years, both central and non-central schools in the Division of Quezon exhibited typically high levels of internal efficiency.

Based on the results presented in Table 2, the following findings were derived:

- 2.1 There is no significant difference in enrolment rate between Central and Non-Central public secondary schools over the last five years, indicating that both school types have comparable capacity in attracting and maintaining student enrolment.

- 2.2 There is no significant difference in promotion rate between Central and Non-Central schools, suggesting that both groups demonstrate similar effectiveness in advancing students to the next grade level.
- 2.3 There is a significant difference in graduation rate between Central and Non-Central schools. Central schools obtained a significantly higher mean graduation rate, indicating stronger performance in ensuring student completion of secondary education.
- 2.4 There is no significant difference in survival rate between the two groups, implying that student retention throughout the schooling cycle is comparable in Central and Non-Central schools.
- 2.5 There is no significant difference in failure rate between Central and Non-Central schools, although Non-Central schools posted a slightly higher mean. The difference, however, is not statistically significant.
- 2.6 There is no significant difference in repetition rate between the two school classifications, showing similar efficiency in minimizing grade repetition.
- 2.7 There is no significant difference in dropout rate between Central and Non-Central schools, indicating that both groups are equally effective in keeping students enrolled until completion.

Overall, the findings reveal that school location (Central vs. Non-Central) does not significantly influence most internal efficiency indicators, except for graduation rate, where Central schools demonstrate a statistically significant advantage.

3. Problems Encountered by Central and Non-Central Schools to School's Internal Efficiency

The findings indicate that problems related to internal efficiency were seldom encountered, with a grand mean of 2.52. Non-central schools consistently reported higher problem levels (mean = 2.65) compared with central schools (mean = 1.96).

3.1. Enrolment rate: Results show that competition from nearby public and private institutions was the most frequently encountered problem, especially in central schools (mean = 4.67). In non-central schools, distance from learners' residences and lack of formal enrolment strategies were sometimes observed.

3.2 Promotion: It was found that problems such as learners failing subjects, inability to meet passing requirements, and family-related pressures were seldom encountered. However, student disengagement was sometimes reported in non-central schools (mean = 2.95).

3.3 Graduation Rate: According to analysis, there were generally few issues with graduation. Although there were sporadic problems in non-central schools related to academic failure and family difficulties, learners who achieved the terminal grade level finished their cycle.

3.4 Survival Rate. The results highlight that health issues (mean = 3.39), frequent transfers (mean = 3.42), and family mobility (mean = 3.37) were sometimes encountered, with non-central schools consistently reporting higher levels compared to central schools.

3.5 Failure Rate

Findings reveal that lack of interest, academic challenges, and absenteeism were sometimes encountered (means = 2.68–3.16). These problems were more pronounced in non-central schools, reflecting disparities in instructional resources and learner support.

3.6 Repetition Rate:

There is evidence linking academic issues and absenteeism to repetition. Non-central schools saw more variations even if repetition rates stayed low, suggesting the need for more robust remedial and enrichment initiatives.

3.7 Dropout Rate

The results show that poverty (mean = 2.84) and low self-confidence (mean = 3.13) were the primary issues in non-central schools. In contrast, bullying and early marriage were rarely encountered across both school categories.

4. Coping Strategies of the Central and Non-Central Schools on the Problems Encountered in School's Internal Efficiency

Schools in the Division of Quezon, both central and non-central, employ a wide range of coping strategies to address internal efficiency challenges, with a grand mean of 4.51, indicating strong institutional commitment.

- 4.1 Enrolment rate: The findings show that highly effective strategies such as early registration campaigns, flexible class schedules, posting enrollment activities on platforms, and teacher participation were consistently practiced (mean = 4.91).
- 4.2 Promotion Rate: Results indicate that strategies including learner performance monitoring, intervention plans, SLAC meetings, and home visitations were highly practiced (mean = 4.69).
- 4.3 Graduation rate: Analysis reveals that parental consultation, home visitation, attendance monitoring, and skill-enhancing activities were consistently implemented (mean = 4.51).
- 4.4 Survival rate: Evidence suggests that health monitoring, school programs, stakeholder recognition, and collaboration with local government units supported retention (mean = 4.36).

- 4.5 **Failure rate:** The results highlight that programs for academically challenged learners, career guidance, instructional materials, and monitoring of teachers' learning action plans were prioritized (mean = 4.29).

4. Intervention Program

A well-defined and structured intervention approach is recommended. The program's main objectives will be community collaboration, parent involvement, learner well-being, and academic support. Giving every student an equal chance to complete their education.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's results led to the following conclusions:

1. The study concludes that both central and non-central public secondary schools in the Division of Quezon demonstrated generally high internal efficiency across the five-year period, as shown by strong performance in enrolment, promotion, survival, and graduation rates. Central schools showed slightly higher and more stable participation, progression, and completion outcomes, indicating a relatively stronger capacity to attract, retain, and sustain learners through the full secondary cycle. Non-central schools also performed commendably, though with greater fluctuations in inefficiency indicators, such as failure, repetition, and dropout rates.
2. Based on the results of the t-test analysis at the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted for enrollment rate, promotion rate, survival rate, failure rate, repetition rate, and dropout rate, indicating no significant difference between Central and Non-Central schools. However, the null hypothesis was rejected for graduation rate, which shows a significant difference between the central and non-central schools.
3. Both central and non-central schools show good internal efficiency. Most learners move up to the next grade and complete each school year. Still, non-central schools experience more problems in enrolment, survival, failure, repetition, and dropout. These problems are often related to poverty, health issues, and families moving from one place to another. In many cases, learners in non-central schools' deal with more personal and financial difficulties. Central schools also face problems, such as competition from nearby schools, but they usually have better facilities and stronger school management. This helps them maintain more stable results.
4. Schools in Quezon use different ways to deal with these challenges. They provide extra academic support to struggling learners, encourage parents to be more involved, and work closely with the community. These efforts help improve enrolment, reduce dropout, and increase promotion and graduation rates. Central schools benefit from stronger institutional support, while non-central schools depend more on cooperation with parents and the local community. Good leadership and teamwork among teachers, parents, and community members are important in keeping schools effective. Overall, the study shows that schools are making progress, but non-central schools need more support to ensure that all learners have the same chance to succeed and finish their education.

Recommendations

The following suggestions were made in light of the findings:

It is recommended that schools, especially non-central ones, get support that fits their needs. This can include giving more resources, improving teaching support, and involving the community more. Doing this will help schools keep improving, handle challenges like limited facilities or disruptions, and make sure all learners have a fair chance to continue and succeed in their education.

1. Based on overall findings on the internal efficiency, Central school showed more stable performance trends, while Non-Central Schools appeared more affected by contextual challenges such as limited resources, and geographic factors. Hence, to address challenges in internal efficiency, non-central schools should:
 - a. Create partnerships from central school for activities like peer tutoring, joint extracurricular programs, and shared community engagement initiatives to promote equitable learner outcomes.
 - b. Establish a regular forum where central schools share best practices for maintaining stable efficiency indicators with non-central schools, focusing on strategies for managing fluctuations in failure, repetition, and dropout rates.
 - c. Allocate additional resources (instructional materials, professional development, and outreach tools) to address the root causes of indicator fluctuations, such as geographic dispersion and socioeconomic vulnerabilities.
 - d. Investigate the specific contextual factors driving fluctuations school's inefficiency indicators to design more tailored interventions.
 - e. Family and community involvement should be strengthened to help learners cope with poverty, family moves, and other social pressures.
 - f. Monitoring systems (like Learner Information System (LIS)) should keep track of enrolment, promotion, survival, and dropout rates so schools can act quickly when needed. At the same time, school management that allows local decision-making and involves the community can help schools solve problems and keep students progressing in their education.

2. Based on the findings, school classification (Central vs. Non-Central) did not significantly influence most internal efficiency indicators, except for graduation rate where central school performed better. The following is being recommended:
 - a. Enhance resource allocation and infrastructure. Non-central school should prioritize funding for upgrading facilities providing adequate instructional materials, and strengthening school management capacities in non-central areas to match the stability of central schools.
 - b. Design and implement programs focused on poverty alleviation support such as: subsidized school supplies, meal/feeding programs, health and wellness services and flexible enrolment processes to accommodate mobile families.
 - c. Implement a needs-based monitoring system. Create a tailored tracking tool that specifically monitors factors linked to non-central schools' challenges (poverty markers, health access, family mobility) and central schools' competition-related issues, to enable proactive and targeted action.
3. The findings indicate that problems related to internal efficiency were seldom encountered, with a grand mean of 2.52. Non-central schools consistently reported higher problem levels (mean = 2.65) compared with central schools (mean = 1.96). Therefore, it is recommended to promote stronger parental and community involvement in supporting learner attendance, motivation, and academic performance.

For Non-Central Schools

- a. Launch a "School-on-Wheels" mobile enrolment twice a year (before opening of classes and mid-year) to reach remote households and families with mobile lifestyles.
- b. Implement a "Learner Tracking System" linked to local barangay offices to monitor students who move, and coordinate with schools in their new location for seamless transfer of records.
- c. Provide monthly stipends for learners from low-income families to cover school supplies, snacks, and transportation costs, fund this through partnerships with local businesses and provincial social welfare offices.
- d. Partner with the Department of Health (DOH) to set up weekly mini-clinics in non-central schools for basic health checks, and referral of students with chronic conditions.
- e. Prioritize non-central schools for government-funded classroom repairs, water/sanitation facilities, and internet connectivity.
- f. Assign experienced central school administrators to serve as part-time "management advisors" for 6-month rotations, focusing on developing enrolment procedures and student support protocols.

For Central Schools

- a. Develop specialized programs such as STEM workshops, sports training, arts clubs that draw students based on interest rather than just proximity, and reserve 10% slots for learners from non-central schools to promote inclusion.
 - b. Collaborate with nearby non-central schools to share facilities like science laboratories or computer rooms on weekends and after hours.
 - c. Establish quarterly "School Leadership Forums" where central and non-central school heads exchange data on student performance, problem-solving strategies, and resource allocation.
 - d. Create a digital repository of best practices in school management, with templates for attendance tracking, parent engagement, and budget planning that non-central schools can adapt.
4. Schools in the Division of Quezon, both central and non-central, employ a wide range of coping strategies to address internal efficiency challenges, with a grand mean of 4.51, indicating strong institutional commitment. It is recommended to sustain and enhance an institutionalized effective coping strategy, such as:
 - a. Document and circulate successful initiatives (e.g., extra academic support models, parent engagement programs) from both central and non-central schools through Quezon Division digital portal and quarterly workshops.
 - b. Create a "Practice Sharing Circle" where 2-3 high performing central schools are paired with non-central schools to co-implement and adapt proven strategies to local contexts.
 - c. Allocate dedicated regional funding to non-central schools for structured academic support programs (e.g., after-school tutorials, remedial classes) and to hire part-time support staff.
 - d. Provide non-central school leaders with formal training in institutional management, grant writing, and resource mobilization -- with mentorship from experienced central school heads.
 - e. Develop a standardized but adaptable "Parent-Community Engagement" for Quezon schools, including clear roles for barangay councils, local NGOs, and business groups in supporting education.
 - f. Implement a "Team Excellence Award" that recognizes schools (especially non-central ones) with outstanding cross stakeholder collaboration and measurable improvements in student outcomes.
 - g. Work with the provincial government to develop a "Learner Equity Fund" that provides targeted support to at-risk students in non-central areas covering costs like school supplies, transportation and health services.

Future Researchers may conduct comprehensive studies in other Schools Division or include additional variables such as economic status, teacher capacity, and school facilities to gain a broader understanding of factors influencing school's internal efficiency.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.